

Perspectives for Teaching Literature: Creative use of Information Technology and New Methods in the Classroom

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Abstract. This article explains the creative use of new methods and IT technologies in grades 5-6 of secondary schools as an effective means of increasing the effectiveness of literary education. Also, the specific features of teaching students to work on a problem, find a solution, prove their opinion, and use an effective storytelling method are discussed.

Key words: literature teaching, IT technologies, discourse analysis methodology, research technologies, essays, critical-creative thinking.

INTRODUCTION.

One of the main objectives of teaching literature is to develop the student's critical and creative thinking. This is done through analysis of the content and text of a work of art. The intended result will be achieved only if the analysis of a work of art is analyzed in relation to the reality of life, if the analysis of the work is based on the principle of the connection between education and life. To achieve this, it is necessary not to include many works in the curriculum, but to select selected works, give them a comprehensive assessment and analyze the work being studied as thoroughly as possible. A pupil needs to learn to understand life, to see the inner essence of human relationships in all its various aspects, by studying works of art in a literature lesson.

It is important for the pupil to be able to evaluate the work he has read. After all, literary education plays a very important role in shaping the student's correct attitude towards the information he receives. The 21 st century is the age of information. Before the student digests the information (information) received in the educational process, social networks on the Internet, the media, television, radio, newspapers, magazines, fiction, the environment, getting to know each other, big and small people read or listen. messages and information. A number of information has a strong influence on his worldview, which has not yet been formed. His young mind is clouded by violent videos broadcast through social media, various types of physical and mental abuse, and the complaints of people who complain that life is full of oppression and injustice. Unfortunately, some young people become depressed as a result. It is very sad that there are even cases of suicide.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

Works included in the school curriculum should be capable of instilling in the student the virtues of justice, patriotism, truthfulness, love of life, strong will, and patriotism that puts public interest above

one's own. In such works of art it is necessary to reflect public hatred of swindlers, thieves and criminals, the rule of law, and the fact that crime does not go unpunished. We cannot always lead the student. We cannot give him the correct interpretation of all works of art and other information. He needs to be able to correctly evaluate a work of art or materials that he receives from other information spaces. The books are also different. Unfortunately, in most foreign publications there are scenes of immorality and debauchery, and in our own television programs there are cases of disdain for women and propaganda of the desire for wealth.

To form a critical attitude towards such works in a student, it is necessary to form critical creative thinking on the basis of educational materials studied at school. Ideologically empty and meaningless works cannot have a harmful effect on a student who has critical and creative thinking and is able to correctly evaluate a work of art. For this reason, it is necessary that the school curriculum in literature, the works of art studied in the literature lesson, and the knowledge that the student receives in the literature lesson direct him to the correct assessment of a range of information. Nowadays, it is good that school textbooks are presented in a special design and beautifully. But the renovation is based not only on the requirements for beautiful design, but also on a perfect analysis of the work of art from all sides. It is necessary to establish the requirements that it must serve for the formation of virtue, which puts public interest above interests and if necessary, the curriculum should be shared with industry and the general public for discussion. Openness and transparency must be ensured.

Of course, the composition of the authors of the textbook in the trinity of scientist-methodologist, teacher and methodologist-practitioner also serves to improve it. If he does not know the field of literature well and does not have the opportunity to evaluate it, if he is not sufficiently familiar with teaching methods at school, if he, as a teacher, does not observe in practice the student's relationship to a work of art, and if he does not strive to keep up with him in the analysis of the work, then for the authors of textbooks his work may be in vain, that is, it may not give the desired result. It is necessary to present the best works of art in the literature program; it is necessary to present the best works of classics and modern writers, taking into account the age and sensitivity of children.

But this should not serve to increase the number of works of art in the curriculum, but to ensure that the selected works, their analysis, and their educational impact on the student are equally effective. That is, it is necessary to ensure that the number of works does not increase, so that each work included in the program has a sufficient impact on the heart and mind of the student, developing creative and critical thinking.

We can say that the curriculum and textbook on literature for grades 5-6 can fully meet the above requirements. The best children's works of Uzbek and world literature are presented here. The question arises. Is the Literature textbook high-quality and effective so that we can raise all students to be readers who love literature? Why doesn't this happen in practice? What needs to be done to achieve this? There is only one answer. Now the effectiveness of studying the subject "Literature" in grades 5-6 depends on the correct organization of the educational process. What should be taken into account:

conducting a literature lesson based on advanced teaching methods and technologies;

effective use of IT technologies in literature lessons;

support the student's initiative and creativity;

the use of discourse analysis in the development of the student's speech, etc. (for example, during the lesson, literary monologues when analyzing the main character of the work, analyzing the conversations of the heroes of the work, memorizing monologues, learning to draw conclusions from the work, etc.).

Hierarchically, this can be expressed as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Factors that increase the effectiveness of a literature lesson in grades 5-6.

The teacher should rely on the initiative of students in a literature lesson and develop their reading skills. It is necessary to increase students' interest in reading and develop the skills of writing a brief explanation of the works they read. Students must write down excerpts from the books they read, explain why they copied this particular part of the work, what aroused their interest in this particular part of the work. Writing creative works, essays, essays is of great importance in literature class. Essay - in French “essai” - “experiment”, in English “essay”, “assay” - aspiration, creative test, essay. The Latin word *exagium* means thinking.

A freely written creative work aimed at expressing personal opinion on literary, philosophical, social, journalistic and other topics in a systematic, non-scientific form is called an essay. This is a unique space for the student to express his feelings and thoughts. In this case, the word is a tool with which the student expresses his free attitude to the topic the way he wants, and provides one or more solutions to the problem. He argues with himself. Expresses doubt, asserts confidence, etc. According to the content, essays are divided into types such as reflective, evidential and descriptive. On average, teenagers only need to write an essay of 200 words or more. The essay also consists of an introduction, a main part and a concluding part based on an indirect internal plan (the plan is not given in the text of the essay).

Writing an essay is one of the effective ways to implement the discourse analysis methodology; it develops the student’s creative writing skills and logical and meaningful manner of speech. Before writing an essay, certain preparations are made. The problem on the topic is studied, a proposed solution is determined, and evidence is collected to support it. The essay should clearly show sincerity and impartiality, you must agree with someone, try to conduct a secret dialogue without lecturing someone's mind. It is necessary to pay attention to the compactness and conciseness of the volume, and if there is too much of it, then you should not use frequently used words and phrases (as well as, etc.) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Requirements for writing an essay

Pupils need to learn how to write a review, that is, evaluate a book. The project method must be used. During the lesson it is planned to study the story "The Thief" by Abdullah Kahkhar. But several students in the class read the work during the holidays and became real fans of the writer. The teacher invites them to discuss the work together and write down the questions that arise, or write down the part of the work they liked and tell why they liked that part. After discussing the work together, students will be able to get answers to questions that they were unable to solve during the class discussion.

This piece will be performed after it has been fully studied in class. First, students work together to find solutions to the questions raised; the teacher summarizes the students' opinions and clarifies some of their provisions. When teaching "The Thief" to write an essay, the teacher first asks students to focus on the problematic issues raised in the work. He talks about the strong impact the work had on the reader and what conclusions can be drawn from it. For example, students could write an essay on this paper as follows.

Example: reflection essay "Crime is inevitably punished" Abdullah Kahhar is my favorite writer. I love him because he always raises the eternal problems of life in his stories. The problems raised in the story "The Thief" are still relevant today. Unfortunately, there are still thieves today. After reading the story, I had a question: who in the story can be called a thief? In my opinion, all the officials who led the grandfather of Kabul astray and left his appeal unanswered are thieves and criminals! The story begins with the theft of Kabul's grandfather's bull. This theft is crushing my grandfather. Poor Grandfather Kabul "with his head uncovered, barefoot, stands at the door and trembles violently, his knees buckle; his eyes widen, he looks at everyone, but sees no one".

The reason is that the land cannot be plowed without oxen. Nothing grows in the uncultivated land. Grandfather will starve along with his family. The worst thing is that the officials who need to find grandfather's ox are only trying to extort something from him. But there is still a little hope. Maybe a centurion, an amin or a bailiff will lend him a helping hand. He finds the dishonest thief and returns the bull to him. Alas, Grandpa Cable's last hope will be dashed. They care about Grandfather Kabul, but do not help him. As a result, Grandfather Kabul is forced to agree to the terms of the cotton merchant Egamberdi in order to receive a bull as collateral.

From the story we can draw the following conclusion: a person should help a person without remuneration. If he wants to get something from a poor person who has asked for help, then the person asking for a bribe is a thief and a criminal. Crime should not go unpunished. Punishment for a crime is inevitable.

Or: The death of a horse is a dog's holiday.

The story "The Thief" by A. Kakhkhar begins with the epigraph "The death of a horse is a dog's holiday." What does the writer mean by quoting this popular proverb? The horse is likened to Grandfather Kabul, and the dog is likened to the thief and officials who shamelessly took bribes from Grandfather Kabul? That's right, grandfather Kabul's bull was stolen and he was helpless. But this was not a case of death! What do the words death and holiday mean? True, grandfather Kabul did not die physically, but died spiritually, he was "broken", his trust was violated. The spiritual "death" of grandfather Kabul, the breakdown of his will, became a holiday for the thief who stole everything, and for officials who are no different from a thief in stealing someone's property. The reason is that they received gifts and bribes that were pleasant to them. In short, the desperation of good people falls on bad people. Woe to the citizens if the country is ruled by dishonest officials!!! Considering that role-playing games have a positive effect on students' knowledge, he can observe the events of the play as performed by pupils.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

A culminating task, animated electronic developments, musical, role-playing games can be very effective teaching tools if they evoke the emotions of students and develop them intellectually.

What needs to be done to ensure that teenagers express their opinions beautifully and effectively? After all, expression shapes thought and deepens feeling. The teenager develops as an individual,

expressing his personality through spoken and written language. To do this, it is necessary to teach the student to work on a problem, find a solution, prove his opinion, and use an effective storytelling style.

Literatures:

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